

1 **Title:** The helper strategy in vector-transmission of plant viruses

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15 **Abstract**

16 An intriguing aspect of vector-transmission of plant viruses is the frequent involvement of a
17 helper component (HC). HCs are virus-encoded non-structural proteins produced in infected
18 plant cells that are mandatory for the transmission success. Over five decades, all data
19 collected on HCs from unrelated viral species transmitted by distinct vector species were
20 consistent with a unique mode of action designated “the bridge hypothesis”: the HC has two
21 functional domains, one binding the virus particle and the other binding a putative receptor in
22 the vector, creating a reversible molecular bridge between the two. This hypothesis
23 appeared fully satisfactory as HCs were reported solely in viruses transmitted non-
24 circulatively -- *i.e.* the virus particle binds externally to the mouthpart of its vector, and can
25 later be released therefrom and inoculated. Recently, however, HCs have also been
26 reported in viruses transmitted circulatively, where the virus particles are internalized in gut
27 cells and cycle within the body to reach the salivary glands. In this more complex scheme of
28 virus-vector interaction, a simple mode of action of HC compatible with the bridge hypothesis
29 becomes questionable. In addition, while it had consistently been shown that the sequential
30 acquisition of HC and virus particles could only work when HC was acquired first, a recent
31 report shows that the reverse acquisition sequence can work in some case, again
32 questioning the bridge hypothesis as a universal mode of action. Because of the importance
33 of HC molecules in the vector-transmission of plant viruses, we here propose an exhaustive
34 review of the field, of its historical perspective and most recent development.

35

36 **1 Introduction**

37 Vector transmission is the mean by which most plant viruses (around 80%) ensure plant-to-
38 plant transfer, and thus maintenance and spread in the environment. Any organism feeding
39 on plants and capable of moving from one plant to another can uptake and release viruses
40 and can potentially act as a vector. Diverse organisms (protists, nematodes, mites and
41 insects) have been reported as efficient vectors, but sap feeding hemipteran insects
42 encompassing plant hoppers, leaf hoppers, and particularly whiteflies and aphids are by far
43 the most important (Nault, 1997; Ng & Falk, 2006; Hogenhout et al., 2008). The mechanisms
44 of virus-vector interaction are also diverse and have been extensively studied in hemipteran
45 insects, which are the major focus of this review. Nevertheless, the classification of the
46 transmission modes of hemipteran insect-transmitted viruses can accommodate cases of
47 transmission by all types of vectors, including mites, nematodes and protists (Blanc, 2008).

48 The two major transmission categories are named non-circulative and circulative (Blanc et al.,
49 2014). In non-circulative transmission, the plant-vector interaction is exclusively external. In
50 hemipteran vectors, the virus reversibly binds to the mouthparts and/or the foregut, where it
51 can be retained for a short time (few minutes to hours) and immediately inoculated to another
52 plant upon salivation or regurgitation. In contrast, in circulative transmission, the interaction is
53 internal. In hemipteran vectors, this means that the virus crosses the gut and circulates within
54 the insect body to reach the salivary glands and ultimately the saliva. Whatever the details of
55 this cycle, it involves an initial specific recognition and the crossing of one or several cellular
56 barriers (at least gut and salivary glands) to accumulate within and be secreted out of the
57 vector. The consequences are the existence of a latent period between acquisition and
58 inoculation, and also, in all reported cases, a high and long-lasting accumulation of the virus
59 that can be transmitted for the whole vector's life span (Blanc et al., 2014). The circulative
60 transmission is divided in the propagative and non-propagative sub-categories, depending on
61 whether the virus replicates or not during its cycle within the vector (Blanc & Gutiérrez, 2015).

62 Regarding molecular interactions with the vector, plant viruses have evolved two distinct
63 strategies, the "capsid strategy" and the "helper strategy" (Pirone & Blanc, 1996). In the capsid
64 strategy, the virus particles are necessary and sufficient to ensure the specific recognition of
65 the vector. The experimental demonstration came from the capacity of the corresponding
66 viruses to be directly acquired from suspensions of purified virus particles, without any other
67 viral proteins, and later transmitted to healthy host plants (Pirone, 1964), demonstrating that
68 the coat protein alone can control attachment (and cycle) within the vector. However, all
69 viruses are not transmissible this way. In addition to the virus particle, a virus-encoded non-

70 structural protein is mandatory for the helper strategy. Many viral species have been shown
71 to require such additional proteins that have been designated “helper components” (HC).
72 Since the first case report for a species of the genus *Potyvirus* (Kassanis & Govier, 1971a),
73 HCs have been described in many other non-circulative virus genera and the helper strategy
74 proved dominant in this transmission category (Syller, 2006). Because HCs of unrelated
75 viruses have no sequence homologies, a specific definition has been provided (Froissart et
76 al., 2002): “a HC can be any compound complying with all of the following criteria: (i) it is virus-
77 encoded, (ii) it can be one or a complex of several non-structural molecules (*i.e.* which can be
78 eliminated upon purification of virions), (iii) it is necessary for the success of vector
79 transmission, and (iv) HC and virions can be acquired sequentially by the vector”.

80 Until today, the HCs from unrelated plant viruses were thought to have the same mode of
81 action, illustrating a convergent evolution, although the selective advantage they may provide
82 remains speculative (Pirone & Blanc, 1996; Froissart et al., 2002). One unexplained
83 longstanding observation was the fact that the helper strategy appears frequent in non-
84 circulative transmission but extremely rare in circulative transmission (Franz et al., 1999).
85 Recent advances are challenging these views by showing that the helper strategy appears
86 widespread in all transmission categories (Grigoras et al., 2018; Lu et al., 2019; Di Mattia et
87 al., 2020), and that distinct HCs may have different modes of action (Di Mattia et al., 2022). In
88 this review, we confront the historical context and the recent discoveries, and we discuss how
89 this wealth of knowledge indicates that HCs may have evolved for diverse reasons in distinct
90 viral clades.

91 **2 A historical perspective on the discovery of helper components**

92 The discovery of HCs and the characterization of their mode of action results exclusively from
93 studies of non-circulatively transmitted viruses. Indeed, as already mentioned above, that the
94 helper strategy also exist in circulative viruses is a very recent finding; it is poorly characterized
95 and will be discussed in a later specific section.

96 The first hint on the discovery of HCs came from (Pirone & Megahed, 1966) who observed
97 that purified particles of the cauliflower mosaic virus (CaMV, genus *Caulimovirus*, Family
98 *Caulimoviridae*) or of the turnip mosaic virus (TuMV, genus *Potyvirus*, family *Potyviridae*) were
99 not transmissible, when acquired through parafilm membranes by aphid vectors. At that time
100 the explanation was unclear and could as well be attributed to partial degradation of virions
101 during the purification process. However, about five years later, key complementary
102 information was reported on the same viral genera. In a series of experiments based on
103 sequential acquisition of transmissible and non-transmissible natural isolates, Kassanis &
104 Govier, and in parallel Lung and Pirone, respectively set the basis of the concept of HC for

105 potyviruses (potato virus Y, PVY, genus *Potyvirus*) and caulimoviruses (CaMV) (**Table 1**).
106 These authors first demonstrated that a non-transmissible isolate could be efficiently
107 transmitted by aphids previously fed on a plant infected with a transmissible isolate of the
108 same viral species, and that the reverse acquisition sequence did not work (Kassanis &
109 Govier, 1971a; b; Lung & Pirone, 1973). These experiments pointed at the existence of a
110 helper factor that would be produced in the plants infected by the transmissible isolate. Such
111 a helper factor could be acquired first by aphids and somewhat be retained and “wait”
112 somewhere in the alimentary tract to complement the transmission of the secondarily acquired
113 non-transmissible isolate. The same authors consistently showed that the transmission of
114 purified virus particles of both poty- and caulimoviruses could be rescued by pre-feeding
115 aphids onto plants infected with a transmissible isolates (Govier & Kassanis, 1974; Lung &
116 Pirone, 1974). Potyvirus-infected plant extracts deprived of virus particles by
117 ultracentrifugation contained HC activity, indicating that the HC is not the virus particle of the
118 transmissible isolate itself (Govier & Kassanis, 1974). Additional chemical, biochemical and
119 immunological treatments of potyvirus-infected plant extracts further demonstrated that the
120 HC is a non-structural protein produced upon infection of plants by a transmissible isolate
121 (Govier et al., 1977). Antisera directed against viral proteins produced from cell-free translation
122 of viral RNA provided the first hint that the HC is virus-encoded by specifically blocking its
123 activity in infected plant-extracts (Hellmann et al., 1983; Thornbury & Pirone, 1983). The
124 copurification of potyviral HC activity and of a viral polypeptide of around 50 KDa further
125 pointed in the same direction (Thornbury et al., 1985). Nevertheless, it was not before the
126 development of molecular biology, particularly the sequencing technology and the production
127 of infectious clones allowing reverse genetic approaches, that the viral origin of HCs could be
128 directly proven.

129 *Potyvirus*

130 The genome of potyviruses is a ss(+)RNA encoding one single large polyprotein precursor,
131 post-translationally cleaved in ten polypeptides, each with one or more specific functions
132 (Allison et al., 1985; Domier et al., 1986; Dougherty & Carrington, 1988). The polypeptide co-
133 purifying with the HC activity (Thornbury et al., 1985) was identified as the second from the N-
134 terminus of the polyprotein (Carrington et al., 1989). Because it also possesses a protease
135 activity, releasing it from the large precursor polyprotein, it was named the helper component
136 proteinase (HC-Pro) (Carrington et al., 1989). Comparison of HC-Pro sequences from
137 transmissible and non-transmissible potyvirus species and isolates pointed at differences in
138 two key regions. The first is located in the N-terminal region (AA positions 50-54) where a
139 conserved “KITC” motif is mutated to EITC in non-transmissible isolates (Thornbury et al.,
140 1990; Granier et al., 1993; Canto et al., 1995). The second is located in the central region (AA

141 positions 308-310) where a conserved “PTK” motif is mutated to PAK in non-transmissible
142 isolates (Huet et al., 1994). The key role of both motifs in HC activity has been thoroughly
143 confirmed by reverse genetics where the introduction of these mutations in transmissible
144 infectious clones always abolished their capacity to be transmitted by aphids (Atreya et al.,
145 1992; Atreya & Pirone, 1993; Huet et al., 1994).

146 Caulimovirus

147 The comparison of the sequence of distinct CaMV isolates revealed that the non-transmissible
148 CM4-184 isolate harbors a 421 bp deletion in the coding region II (gene II) (Howell & Hull,
149 1978; Howarth et al., 1981). These authors thereby established that gene II was dispensable
150 for plant infection, pointing at its specific function in aphid-transmission. This was soon
151 confirmed by the demonstration that deletion or mutation of this genome region in
152 transmissible CaMV isolates were associated with the loss of transmissibility (Armour et al.,
153 1983; Daubert et al., 1983; Woolston et al., 1983, 1987). The product of gene II, the protein
154 P2, has then been produced in the heterologous baculovirus/insect cell system (Espinoza et
155 al., 1992), in a biologically active form able to complement the transmission of CaMV non-
156 transmissible isolates acquired from infected plants or crude extracts thereof (Blanc et al.,
157 1993). Intriguingly, this heterologous-expressed P2 failed to complement the transmission of
158 purified CaMV particle, suggesting the possible requirement for an additional unknown factor
159 (Blanc et al., 1993). Finally, this additional compound was identified as the viral protein P3
160 (product of gene III) that must be present in the purified CaMV particle suspension for
161 successful complementation of aphid-transmission by the previously acquired P2 (Leh et al.,
162 1999). Thus, two non-structural proteins, P2 and P3, assist the vector-transmission of CaMV.
163 While P2 meets the four criteria defining a HC (Froissart et al., 2002), P3 does not. Indeed, its
164 acquisition together with CaMV virions is mandatory for successful vector-transmission
165 (Drucker et al., 2002). As P3 cannot be acquired separately from virions, it cannot be qualified
166 as a HC.

167 While the helper strategy has been extensively studied for the genera *Caulimovirus* and
168 *Potyvirus*, it has also been reported in other genera of the family *Potyviridae*: *Ipomovirus* with
169 viruses transmitted by whiteflies (Colinet et al., 1998) and *Tritimovirus* with viruses transmitted
170 by mites (Stenger et al., 2005; Stenger et al., 2005; Stenger et al., 2006) (**Table 1**). The
171 requirement of HC molecules has even been evidenced in the genus *Tobravirus* (Family
172 *Virgaviridae*) transmitted by nematodes in a non-circulative manner (MacFarlane et al., 1999)
173 (**Table 1**). Hence, helper components appear to have evolved in unrelated viruses transmitted
174 non-circulatively by distinct vectors. Unfortunately, in depth characterization of their mode of
175 action remain limited to a few emblematic cases within the poty- and caulimoviruses.

176 **3 Modes of action of helper components**

177 The repeated observation that successful transmission resulted either from the concomitant
178 acquisition of the HC and virus particle, or from their sequential acquisition solely if the HC is
179 acquired first, allowed the pioneer research groups working on potyviruses (Kassanis &
180 Govier, 1971b; a) and caulimoviruses (Lung & Pirone, 1973, 1974) to propose an hypothesis
181 describing the mode of action of HCs. The HC would specifically bind to a receptor molecule
182 within the vector and to the virus particle (or to a viral partner fixed on the virus particle in the
183 case of CaMV), through distinct functional domains, thereby creating a molecular link between
184 the two. This hypothesis, later named the “bridge hypothesis” (Pirone & Blanc, 1996) became
185 widely accepted and, so far, nearly all empirical investigations on the question yielded
186 supportive results. Remarkably, recent data on the existence of HCs in circulative viral species
187 is casting doubts or at least calling for nuances and careful reexamination (see the dedicated
188 section IV).

189

190 **3.1 Helper component – virus particle interaction**

191 *Potyvirus*

192 As indicated in the previous section, reverse genetic approaches identified two important
193 domains of the potyviral HC-Pro, respectively containing the motifs KITC and PTK. In parallel,
194 comparison of coat protein sequences pointed out the highly conserved amino acid triplet DAG
195 that appears to be mutated to DAE in some of the analyzed non transmissible isolates
196 (Harrison & Robinson, 1988). Directed mutagenesis in infectious clones of various potyviral
197 species, changing the triplet DAG to DAE, systematically resulted in the loss of aphid-
198 transmissibility (Atreya et al., 1990, 1995; Gal-On et al., 1992). Noticeably, the DAG motif is
199 located at the N-terminus of the coat protein, in a region predicted to be accessible at the
200 surface of virus particle, potentially available for binding to HC-Pro (Shukla & Ward, 1989).
201 The experimental demonstration of a direct interaction between HC-Pro and the capsid of
202 *Tobacco vein mottling virus* (TVMV) was obtained using a protein blotting-overlay protocol
203 where the HC-Pro extracted from infected plants was assessed for specific binding onto full
204 length or truncated coat protein. HC-Pro was shown to interact with a 7 amino acid sequence
205 (DTV DAGK) encompassing the DAG motif, and this interaction was totally abolished by the
206 DAE mutation. Several amino acid substitutions were performed within the DTV DAGK
207 sequence and used to demonstrate a perfect correlation between HC-Pro/coat protein binding
208 and successful aphid transmission (Blanc et al., 1997) (Figure 1). The HC-Pro-CP interaction
209 was then reported for other potyviruses (Peng et al., 1998) and the PTK amino acid triplet
210 identified as the HC-Pro motif recognizing the DAG of the coat protein (Peng et al., 1998)

211 (Figure 1). Further experimental evidence came from a study on the specificity of the binding
212 between HC-Pro and CP. The HC-Pro of zucchini yellow mosaic virus (ZYMV) cannot
213 complement the transmission of TuMV particles, and *vice versa*. Replacing the N-terminal
214 region of the coat protein of ZYMV by that of TuMV allowed the aphid transmission of the
215 recombinant virus complemented by the HC-Pro of TuMV (Wang et al., 1998). This result
216 strongly suggested that the N-terminal region of the CP containing the DAG motif is the sole
217 determinant of the binding of potyvirus particles to HC-Pro (Figure 1).

218 Caulimovirus

219 Protein overlay assays demonstrated a more complex situation for CaMV (Schmidt et al.,
220 1994). The HC (the protein P2) efficiently attached virions from infected plant crude extracts
221 but not from purified virus suspensions. The mandatory additional component eliminated upon
222 purification was later found to be the viral protein P3 (Leh et al., 1999, 2001; Drucker et al.,
223 2002), that decorates virus particles, with its C-terminus deeply anchored into pores opened
224 in between capsid hexamers, and its N-terminus exposed at the surface and binding to P2
225 (Plisson et al., 2005; Hoh et al., 2010) (Figure 1). It is remarkable that P3 adopts a tetrameric
226 parallel conformation when free in solution and a different one when anchored to the virion,
227 and that only the latter conformation has an affinity for a functional multimeric form of P2
228 (Hebrard et al., 2001; Hoh et al., 2010). These studies further determined that the virion-bound
229 P3 forms a network of N-terminal antiparallel coiled-coil dimers that bind to a coiled coil trimer
230 of the C-terminal moiety of P2 (Figure 1).

231 3.2 Helper component – aphid receptor interaction

232 Potyvirus

233 In the case of potyviruses, seminal work by Bradley and Ganong (Bradley & Ganong, 1955a;
234 b) showed that irradiation or chemical treatment with formaldehyde of the stylet's tip of
235 viruliferous aphids inhibited subsequent inoculation of PVY, suggesting that the infectious
236 virus material was retained at the corresponding location. Consistently, autoradiography of
237 labeled virions as well as optical, electron, and more recently fluorescent microscopy, showed
238 that potyviruses can be detected throughout the alimentary tract, but that they are mainly
239 retained at the distal tip of the aphid stylets (Ammar et al., 1994; Wang et al., 1996; Mondal et
240 al., 2021). Transmission assays with various potyviruses and aphid species demonstrated that
241 the transmission success depends largely on the HC-Pro/aphid species combination, and this
242 was considered a first indication of the probable existence of specific receptors of HC-Pro
243 within aphid stylets (Wang et al., 1998).

244 We here again refer to the two conserved amino acid motifs, KITC and PTK, respectively
245 located in the N-terminal and central regions of HC-Pro. While, as indicated above, mutations

246 in the PTK motif abolish the binding to the coat protein (Huet et al., 1994), changes in KITC
247 motif (and even in a larger N-terminal domain) do not but instead impair retention within the
248 stylets (Blanc et al., 1998) (Figure 1). Biochemical and structural analysis of HC-Pro revealed
249 its capacity to self-interact and form oligomers (Thornbury et al., 1985; Plisson et al., 2003;
250 Ruiz-Ferrer et al., 2005), and Ruiz-Ferrer and colleagues (2005) further speculated that this
251 oligomerization drives a geometrical arrangement and generates two functional domains,
252 which could respectively bind to virion and to a receptor in the stylets.

253 An elegant study, combining the electrical control of aphid feeding behavior and transmission
254 testing, demonstrated that the acquisition of a potyvirus is associated to ingestion of infected
255 plant cell content, whereas the inoculation is associated to salivation (Powell, 2005). The food
256 canal where the sap is streaming up and the salivary canal where the saliva is streaming down
257 are separated all along the stylets, but at the extreme distal tip where they fuse to form the
258 “common canal”. The authors logically concluded that the HC-Pro-virion complexes should be
259 retained in the common canal, because it is the only location in contact with both ingested
260 plant material and ejected saliva. Despite the fact that all available experimental data are
261 compatible with the bridge hypothesis (Dombrovsky et al., 2007; Fernandez-Calvino et al.,
262 2010; Kamangar et al., 2019), the identity of the receptor of HC-Pro within the common canal
263 remains elusive. Stylets being cuticular tissues, cuticular proteins are of course expected to
264 play a role in potyvirus binding and represent the best receptor candidates, but the proof is
265 still lacking.

266 Caulimovirus

267 Just as for potyviruses, the domain of the CaMV P2 that recognizes the putative receptor
268 within the aphid stylets has been localized by mutagenesis approaches in the N-terminal
269 domain of the protein. In particular, the identity of the residue at amino acid position 6 appears
270 to be key for aphid/virus recognition. In the CaMV Cabb-BJI isolate, replacement of the
271 glutamine at this position by other residues differentially affected the transmission efficiency
272 by distinct aphid species. One of these mutants, where a tyrosine substituted for the glutamine,
273 named mutant P2-Rev5, could no longer be transmitted by any aphid species (Moreno et al.,
274 2005).

275 A major advance in this field of research came from the development of an efficient in vitro
276 binding assay between the heterologously-expressed CaMV P2 and dissected aphid maxillary
277 stylets (Uzest et al., 2007). This system confirmed that the P2-Rev5 mutant does not bind to
278 the stylets whereas the wild type P2 is specifically retained within the common canal, onto an
279 unforeseen cuticular structure that has been named the “acrostyle” (Uzest et al., 2010) (Figure
280 1). Initially reported as displaying cuticular proteins at its surface, the acrostyle has been

281 further characterized and its proteome is now available (Webster et al., 2017, 2018; Deshoux
282 et al., 2020). Of important note is the identification of proteins from the CPR and CPAP3
283 families, named Stylin-01 to Stylin-05, that have one of their domains emerging and accessible
284 at the surface of the acrostyle (Figure 1). All of these proteins stand as prime receptor
285 candidates for non-circulative viruses and, consistently, Stylin-01 was shown to be involved in
286 CaMV transmission and has been proposed to act as receptor for this virus (Webster et al.,
287 2018) (Figure 1). Unfortunately, cuticular proteins are extremely difficult to handle. Their
288 biochemical and structural properties are virtually unknown, and further effort is needed to
289 achieve heterologous production in a correctly folded and fully functional form. This technical
290 bottleneck has been holding for decades and has thus far precluded the definitive validation
291 of HC–receptor interaction. Breaking this lock would pave the way for the search of receptors
292 of potyviruses and/or cucumoviruses, potentially among the Stylins described in the acrostyle,
293 and for the development of antagonistic compounds able to specifically block virus-vector
294 interactions.

295 As indicated earlier, studies of the HC mode of action in non-circulative virus clades other than
296 caulimo- and potyviruses are scarce. To briefly mention in the frame of this review, the reports
297 on HC-Pro in distinct genera of the family *Potyviridae*, transmitted by whiteflies or even mites,
298 all assume a mode of action similar to that in the genus *Potyvirus* transmitted by aphids
299 (Colinet et al., 1998; Stenger et al., 2005). Likewise, investigation of the mode of action of the
300 HC in tobnaviruses indicated that virus particles can be retained in the anterior part of the
301 feeding apparatus of nematode vectors only when a compatible HC is also present and
302 associated to virions, again supporting the bridge hypothesis (MacFarlane et al., 1999;
303 Vassilakos et al., 2001).

304

305 **Figure 1: Schematization of the HC mode of action for noncirculative viruses**
 306 **transmitted by aphids.** (a) *Potyvirus*: shows Hc-Pro attached to putative receptors.
 307 (b) *CaMV*: show the HC (P2) bound to putative receptor; P4 is the coat protein; P3
 308 forms a network around the virus particle. At the distal tip of the aphid stylets, the
 309 acrostyle (c) harbors cuticular proteins named Stylins (Stylin-01 to -05). All known or
 310 suspected stylet-HC-virus particle interactions and the involved protein domains
 311 (when identified) are detailed in the magnifications on the right

312

313 3.3 Transmission activation

314 At least the two best-studied groups of non-circulative viruses, potyviruses and
 315 caulimoviruses, have evolved a remarkably sophisticated cellular response to the feeding of
 316 the insect vectors on infected plants. This response results in the immediate formation of
 317 specific viral transmission morphs that are efficiently acquired by the vectors. In both cases,
 318 the helper component is a key player of this phenomenon that has been called "Transmission
 319 Activation" or TA (Drucker & Then, 2015).

320 Within infected plant cells, the three components of the CaMV transmissible complexes, P2,
321 P3 and virions, are separated in distinct compartments. Most of the virus particles are
322 accumulated, likely as P3-virion complexes, in several electron-dense inclusions that have
323 been identified as the viral factories. P2 is not detectable in these viral factories. Instead, P2
324 entirely accumulates in one unique electron-lucent inclusion per infected cell, that also contain
325 P3 and a few scattered virions (Drucker et al., 2002), and that is designated the transmission
326 body (TB). A series of studies uncovered a phenomenon where the CaMV can reversibly
327 produce transmissible complexes, precisely when needed, when aphids puncture plant cells
328 and ingest a minute amount of their content (Martinière et al., 2009; Martiniere et al., 2013;
329 Bak et al., 2013). Upon puncturing an infected plant, the stylets and/or secreted saliva trigger
330 a plant response, likely involving calcium fluctuation and ROS production, which is
331 immediately hijacked by the virus. Within less than ten seconds, the TB is first loaded with
332 tubulin and then disintegrates and disperses P2 all over the cell cytoplasm onto the
333 microtubule network (Martiniere et al., 2013). Within the same short time frame, P3-virion
334 complexes are expelled from the viral factories and also totally cover the microtubule network,
335 likely associating with P2 (Bak et al., 2013). The authors showed that transmissible complexes
336 thereby become accessible all over the cell probed by an aphid vector, and further
337 demonstrated that the situation reversed to the initial stage within 5 minutes of aphid
338 departure, with the reconstitution of genuine TB (Martiniere et al., 2013) and virion-loaded viral
339 factories (Bak et al., 2013).

340 A comparable observation has been reported by the same research group for potyviruses
341 (Berthelot et al., 2019). While the phenomenon of transmission activation can be considered
342 analogous, the molecular/cellular processes involved are totally distinct (Berthelot et al.,
343 2019). In this case, both the virus particles of TuMV and the HC-Pro are homogeneously
344 distributed over the cytoplasm of infected plant cells. The signal of the aphid puncture and its
345 transduction by the plant, possibly also involving calcium spiking and ROS production, induces
346 an immediate oligomerization of HC-Pro, and this conformational change appears to promote
347 the formation of HC-Pro-virion complexes within the cell. The same study again demonstrates
348 that this phenomenon is reversible after a few minutes from the triggering signal, with
349 disappearance of the oligomeric forms of HC-Pro within infected tissues.

350 In the two cases, one may wonder why a virus would adopt such a complex “behavior” when
351 a constitutive production of transmissible complexes in infected tissues would appear easier
352 and efficient. The explanation provided by the authors is that viral proteins are often
353 multifunctional and have many duties to fulfill. For example, CaMV-P3 complexes also bind to
354 P1 for cell-to-cell and long-distance movement within the plant (Stavolone et al., 2005) and
355 the domain of P3 involved in binding to P1 is the same as that binding to P2. The HC-Pro of

356 potyviruses has multiple functions (Valli et al., 2018), many of which may not be compatible
357 with the oligomeric form binding to the virus particles upon aphid punctures. In simple words,
358 the transmissible complexes may interfere with other step of the viral life cycle and their
359 transient appearance just when needed may alleviate the problem.

360 Whether TA is a general phenomenon that could be extended to the transmission of many
361 others viral species is a formidable avenue of research in the near future, even beyond plant
362 virology (Blanc & Gutiérrez, 2015). Likewise, whether it is limited to non-circulative
363 transmission and more specifically whether HC molecules should always be involved is also
364 a relevant and stimulating question.

365 **4 The helper strategy in circulative viruses**

366 The helper strategy has long been believed to be restricted to the non-circulative transmission,
367 though no explanation could be provided. There was one report, mentioning the involvement
368 of an HC in the aphid transmission of a nanovirus (Genus *Nanovirus*, Family *Nanoviridae*)
369 (Franz et al., 1999), but the molecular details were not investigated for nearly two decades.
370 This uncharacterized HC controlling the transmission of a circulative non-propagative
371 nanovirus remained the exception confirming the rule until recently. The discovery of the
372 involvement of a HC in the leafhopper transmission of the circulative propagative rice stripe
373 virus (RSV, genus *Tenuivirus* Family *Phenuiviridae*, Order *Bunyavirales*) confirmed that a
374 helper strategy can evolve whatever the category of virus-vector interaction (Lu et al., 2019)
375 (Table 1). An interesting and timely question is now whether the bridge hypothesis stands as
376 the universal mode of action of HCs.

377 *Tenuiviruses*

378 Most members of the order *Bunyavirales* have a lipid envelope associated with two
379 glycoproteins Gn and Gc involved in membrane fusion and entry into host cells (Guardado-
380 Calvo & Rey, 2017). Tenuiviruses appear to have lost their lipid envelop but still produce the
381 two glycoproteins, which are in this case non-structural proteins respectively named NSvc2-N
382 and NSvc2-C (Chen et al., 2019), deriving from the cleavage of the precursor glycoprotein
383 NSvc2. The non-enveloped virus particles appear as filamentous ribonucleoproteins
384 (Toriyama, 1986) and, interestingly, they cannot be transmitted by their plant hopper vectors
385 when purified (Lu et al., 2019). The adjunction of the two glycoproteins to purified
386 ribonucleoproteins efficiently rescued the vector transmission of rice stripe virus (Lu et al.,
387 2019). The same authors further demonstrated that the two proteins can interact with the virus
388 particle. NSvc2-N connects it to a putative receptor at the surface of the insect gut cells and
389 triggers endocytosis. NSvc2-C subsequently allows the release of the virion-NSvc2-N complex

390 from endosomes into the cytosol, presumably through a membrane fusion activity whose
391 precise mode of action remains elusive in the specific case of tenuiviruses (Figure 2a).

392 These results are seemingly compatible with the bridge hypothesis, at least for NSvc2-N (Yao
393 et al., 2014), but some aspects need further investigations. In particular, it is unclear whether
394 NSvc2-C can be acquired sequentially or whether a co-acquisition with the virion and/or
395 NSvc2-N is mandatory. Because Gn and Gc of bunyaviruses are generally forming
396 heterodimers (Hepojoki et al., 2010), it would also be interesting to test a possible co-
397 acquisition of NSvc2-N and NSvc2-C as a unique complex that could complement the ulterior
398 acquisition and transmission of purified viral particles.

399 Nanoviruses

400 Analogous to approaches earlier developed for non-circulative poty- or caulimoviruses (see
401 section 2), Franz and coworkers discovered that the aphid transmission of purified faba bean
402 necrotic yellows virus (FBNYV, genus *Nanovirus*) particles was not possible, unless the aphid
403 vectors were previously fed on a plant infected by a transmissible isolate (Franz et al., 1999)
404 (Table 1). Similar pre-feeding on an infected plant was also required for the transmission of
405 purified viral particles directly injected into the aphid hemolymph. Although its viral origin was
406 not proven, the authors concluded that a HC was most likely produced in infected plants and
407 necessary for the virus to cross the gut and salivary gland cell barriers. Unfortunately, both
408 the identity and the mode of action of this putative HC remained unexplored after this seminal
409 work, even long after infectious clones of nanoviruses became available.

410 The family *Nanoviridae* regroups viruses which genome is composed of six (genus *Babuvirus*)
411 or eight (genus *Nanovirus*) circular ssDNA segments, individually encapsidated in distinct viral
412 particles and each encoding a single protein (Gronenborn, 2004; Lal et al., 2020). Infectious
413 clones could be successfully produced for several member species of the genus *Nanovirus*
414 (Timchenko et al., 2006; Grigoras et al., 2009, 2014, 2018), but so far failed for babuviruses.
415 Because of the nature of these infectious constructs, one clone per genomic segment, these
416 authors realized that some segments could be omitted upon inoculation without compromising
417 the systemic infection of host plants (Timchenko et al., 2006; Grigoras et al., 2018). They were
418 then able to demonstrate that in the absence of the segment N, the host plant appeared
419 systemically infected but aphid transmission from this plant was impossible (Grigoras et al.,
420 2018). Modifications of the start codon or coding sequence further showed that the HC of
421 nanoviruses is not the segment N itself but its encoded NSP protein (Grigoras et al., 2018; Di
422 Mattia et al., 2020).

423 The localization of the coat protein of banana bunchy top babuvirus in its aphid vector
424 indicated that the virus accumulates at only two locations, the anterior midgut and the principal

425 salivary glands (Bressan & Watanabe, 2011; Watanabe & Bressan, 2013). Di Mattia and co-
 426 workers (Di Mattia et al., 2020) recently re-investigated this localization for faba bean necrotic
 427 stunt virus (FBNSV, genus *Nanovirus*), in the presence/absence of the segment N. Not only
 428 did they observe that this segment was mandatory for the internalization of the virus and its
 429 accumulation in the aphid gut cells, but also that the NSP protein colocalized therein with both
 430 viral DNA and coat protein. This observation is reminiscent of that described for NScv2-N of
 431 tenuiviruses (Lu et al., 2019) and again compatible with the bridge hypothesis. The NSP
 432 protein may attach to the viral particles on one side and to a gut (and/or salivary gland) cell
 433 receptor on the other side and trigger the endocytosis of the complex (Di Mattia et al., 2020).
 434 However, most recent incongruent observations are now casting doubts (Figure 2b).
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Figure 2: Schematization of the hypothetical mode of action of HC for circulative viruses transmitted by hemipteran insects. The mode of action of HC in circulative propagative transmission of tenuiviruses is summarized on the left. The mode of action of the HC of circulative non propagative nanoviruses is shown on the right. There is a clear lack of molecular details that are currently awaiting further investigation.

442

443 A thorough characterization of protein-protein interactions was conducted between the eight
444 proteins of another nanovirus, the pea necrotic yellow dwarf virus (PNYDV), using bimolecular
445 fluorescence complementation (BiFC) (Krenz et al., 2017). This approach revealed that NSP
446 interacts with itself and with M-Rep (the replication-associated protein) but, surprisingly, not
447 with the coat protein CP. Because an interaction between NSP and CP has since then been
448 reported for babuviruses (Ji et al., 2019; Yu et al., 2019), this question deserves further
449 investigation for nanoviruses and the two possibility – direct NSP/CP interaction or not – are
450 envisaged in Figure 2b. In the BiFC system, the fusion of fluorescent reporter protein to NSP
451 protein of FBNSV may have hindered the interaction with CP.

452 One highly consistent observation on the action of HCs in non-circulative transmission is that
453 it must be acquired first, prior to the virus particles, the reverse acquisition sequence being
454 systematically inefficient. This has always been interpreted as related to the capacity of the
455 helper to recognize its receptor in the vector mouthparts or foregut, while the virus particle
456 cannot directly do this and is “flushed” with the digestive flux/transit when acquired first and
457 alone. Recent work from our laboratory yielded a contradicting observation (Di Mattia et al.,
458 2022). As mentioned above, some genome segments of nanoviruses can be omitted at
459 inoculation of host plants and we made use of this possibility to design sequential acquisition
460 experiments. Plants infected with either the segment N or the segment U4 missing
461 (respectively named FBNSV-N⁽⁻⁾ and FBNSV-U4⁽⁻⁾) exhibit symptoms similar to those resulting
462 from wild type FBNSV infection, and FBNSV-U4⁽⁻⁾ is perfectly transmissible by aphid while
463 FBNSV-N⁽⁻⁾ is not (Grigoras et al., 2018). In fact, U4 is completely dispensable for infection
464 and aphid transmission under laboratory conditions. According to the current understanding
465 of the mode of action of HCs, aphids fed first on the FBNSV-U4⁽⁻⁾ infected plants should
466 acquire NSP and subsequently complement the acquisition and transmission of the segment
467 U4 from FBNSV-N⁽⁻⁾ infected plants. In contrast, in the reverse acquisition sequence, U4-
468 containing virus particles should not be internalized in and transmitted by aphid, due to the
469 absence of NSP protein in the first acquisition from FBNSV-N⁽⁻⁾ plants, and due to their
470 absence in the second acquisition from FBNSV-U4⁽⁻⁾ plants. To our surprise, U4 segment was
471 as efficiently internalized in and transmitted by aphids whatever the sequence of acquisition
472 (Di Mattia et al., 2022). This proved true even when aphids were “purged” on healthy plants
473 for up to 2 days in between the two acquisition phases. This observation is intriguing and is
474 further discussed in the last section. It demonstrates that, in the case of nanoviruses, the HC
475 can expectedly wait for virions within the aphid, but that the virions can somewhat
476 unexpectedly wait for the HC for at least two days without being flushed out by the digestive
477 flux.

478 **5 New perspectives and prospects**

479 5.1 What is a helper component?

480 When Froissart and colleagues (Froissart et al., 2002) proposed the extended definition of
481 HC, the helper-dependent strategy was almost exclusively described for non-circulative
482 viruses. Most knowledge on the nature and mode of action of HCs were based on the thorough
483 characterization of the best-studied cases, P2 of CaMV and HC-Pro of potyviruses, but the
484 proposed definition also accounted for the fragmentary data on HCs of other virus groups
485 available at that time (Table 1). Since then, additional reports have been published, the most
486 intriguing being those confirming the existence of the helper strategy in circulative
487 transmission (Grigoras et al., 2018; Lu et al., 2019; Di Mattia et al., 2020, 2022). In all cases,
488 HCs are non-structural proteins encoded by the virus and they are mandatory for the success
489 of vectors transmission. One key feature of HCs that is confronted by these recent findings is
490 the sequential acquisition of HC and virions. While the sequential acquisition was always
491 shown to be possible solely if the HC is acquired first, the study of a circulative nanovirus (Di
492 Mattia et al., 2022) proved that the reverse sequence also works in this viral system. At this
493 stage, it is not clear whether this observation is inherent to a distinct mode of action of HCs in
494 circulative viruses, because the only other HC characterized for another circulative virus, the
495 phenuivirus RSV (Lu et al., 2019), has not been tested when acquired after the virus particles.

496 The sequential acquisition has been proposed as a key feature of HCs because it allows HC-
497 trans-complementation, *i.e.* the HC encoded by a genome X in a virus population can assist
498 the transmission of a genome Y from the same population or from another population in
499 another host plant, allowing cooperation between related viral genomes at the transmission
500 step rather than competition (Pirone & Blanc, 1996). It is noticeable that, in this view, the
501 sequence of acquisition does not matter, and so the current definition of HCs still perfectly
502 holds for all cases reported to date.

503 5.2 How does a helper component work

504 The sole mode of action of HCs reported to date is the bridge hypothesis extensively described
505 in previous sections. This hypothesis derives from the observation that HCs have to be present
506 for the virus particle to be efficiently retained or internalized in the vector. Without HC, virions
507 are supposedly flushed together with the flux in the digestive track, explaining why the HC
508 have to be acquired either prior to or together with the virus particles. Clearly, the fact that the
509 HC of nanoviruses (the NSP protein) can efficiently mediate the aphid transmission of virus
510 particles acquired several days ahead is questioning its mode of action. The virus particles
511 could somehow be retained within the gut lumen of aphid vectors and be internalized and
512 accumulate within epithelial gut cells solely through the action of the protein NSP. This is

513 opening several possibilities that are calling for further investigation. The virus particles could
514 be retained in the gut lumen non-specifically, embedded in gut cell secretions or stuck in
515 between the microvilli, but they could also be specifically attached to membrane receptors.
516 Investigating the viral determinants of nanovirus-aphid specificity would answer this question.
517 Then the NSP protein acquired later could trigger endocytosis of virions or of NSP-virion
518 complexes. Additional role of NSP in transcytosis, and release of virus particles into the
519 hemolymph are also conceivable and would all represent a mode of action significantly distinct
520 from the classical bridge hypothesis.

521

522 5.3 Why are helper components so frequently involved in the vector transmission of plant
523 viruses

524 The distinction between capsid and helper strategies in vector-transmission of viruses has
525 been conceptualized and empirically studied solely in plant virology (Blanc & Gutiérrez, 2015).
526 The requirement of an HC for successful virus-vector interaction have been confirmed
527 countless times, on totally unrelated viruses, transmitted by unrelated vectors, through
528 different mechanisms (Hogenhout et al., 2008; Dietzgen et al., 2016; Lu et al., 2019).
529 Therefore, the helper strategy certainly evolved several times independently, indicating that it
530 likely confers a selective benefit, at least in some environmental conditions. Paradoxically,
531 because it requires the production of an additional viral protein to ensure virus transmission,
532 the helper strategy may incur a cost to the virus when compared to the capsid strategy.
533 However, some HCs interact with various partners (other viral, host plant or vector molecules)
534 at different steps of the virus cycle, either in the vector or within the host plant where they
535 ensure important and diverse functions. A case study is the multi-tasking protein HC-Pro of
536 potyviruses involved in many different processes (Valli et al., 2018). This multifunctionality
537 may compensate for the cost associated to the maintenance of a helper protein and may
538 instead confer specific benefit to viruses. But not all HCs are known to be multifunctional and
539 so the benefit they may provide remains largely elusive. Their possible multifarious mode of
540 action in distinct viral clades may stem from the fact that each of these clades have evolved
541 HCs with their own molecular means, and the question of whether the selective pressure that
542 drove this evolution are similar in all cases is an interesting issue. In other words, whether all
543 HCs have been selected for the same reason, and for what reason, is a complete mystery for
544 which some speculations are provided below.

545 Cooperation hypothesis

546 A long-standing proposition is that HCs could result from selection at the quasispecies/virus
547 population level (Pirone & Blanc, 1996). According to these authors, HC allows cooperation

548 between genomes of a viral population (or of distinct populations located in different host
549 plants) during vector transmission, whereas the capsid strategy does not. If a genome within
550 a population produces a HC that is adapted to the dominant vector species in a given place
551 and at a given time, it will assist the transmission of other genomes acquired through HC-
552 Trans-complementation that do not produce such adapted HC. The consequence is the
553 relaxing of the bottleneck associated to selection by the vector and maintenance of a higher
554 polymorphisms in the transmitted populations. This hypothetical benefit could apply to all virus
555 species with the helper strategy, but unfortunately no experimental support has been provided,
556 and a way to test for it is even hard to imagine.

557 Collective transmission hypothesis

558 An important proportion (that can be up to 100%) of virions from viral populations of most virus
559 species appears to contain defective genomes (for reviews on defective particles see (Sun &
560 Brooke, 2018; Vignuzzi & López, 2019), or only part of the genetic information (for a review
561 on multipartite virus see (Michalakis & Blanc, 2020), resulting in a possible benefit of co-
562 transmitting several particles to the same host (or cell within this host) in order to restore
563 infectivity. This view of a viral infectious unit as a “collective infectious unit” has been
564 extensively reviewed, and in particular the mechanisms through which viruses can achieve
565 collective transmission (Sanjuán & Thoulouze, 2019; Shirogane et al., 2019). While the
566 mechanisms invoked include the incorporation of several genomes in the same capsid
567 (bacteriophage), the passage of large amounts of virus particles through virus-induced
568 nanotubes connecting distinct cells or through membrane vesicles transferring in viral
569 synapses (HIV, Influenza, Herpesvirus), the formation of virion aggregates with spontaneous
570 binding between particles (vesicular stomatitis virus), or the multi-virion complexes found in
571 occlusion bodies of baculoviruses, HCs have not been hypothesized to potentially facilitate
572 collective transmission. Most characterized HC have been demonstrated to bind the virus coat
573 protein (Blanc et al., 1997; Peng et al., 1998; Plisson et al., 2005; Hoh et al., 2010; Lu et al.,
574 2019; Ji et al., 2019), to also self-interact (Hebrard et al., 2001; Ruiz-Ferrer et al., 2005;
575 Hepojoki et al., 2010; Krenz et al., 2017), and thus to possibly trigger aggregation of virus
576 particles. For example, we have demonstrated that the genome segments of nanoviruses
577 acquired simultaneously (Di Mattia et al., 2020) or even sequentially (Di Mattia et al., 2022) by
578 the aphid vector accumulate all together in the same intracellular aggregates in the AMG cells
579 solely if a functional segment N encoding the NSP protein is present in infected plants.
580 Nanoviruses being multipartite, collective transmission of several viral particles may appear
581 immediately beneficial (Michalakis & Blanc, 2020). However, HCs have been described in
582 numerous monopartite viruses, suggesting that, under this hypothesis, collective transmission
583 would be beneficial whatever the genome architecture/organization.

584 The effector hypothesis

585 When entering a cell, viruses have to manipulate its defenses to initiate infection (Wu et al.,
586 2019). This is true for many intracellular pathogens, including bacteria and fungi, which
587 release effector proteins hampering cell-defense and facilitating infection. When injected into
588 a new plant by a vector, one viral protein that is first in contact with the host cell is the coat
589 protein. While its putative contribution to counter cell defenses has been envisaged and
590 discussed (Conti et al., 2017; Nicaise & Candresse, 2017; Wu et al., 2019), that HCs could
591 also be released together with virions and act as early pathogen effectors has not been
592 envisaged. Most if not all HCs of non-circulative and circulative viruses could be
593 multifunctional proteins. Beyond constituting a molecular bridge linking the virus particles to
594 vector receptors, HCs also frequently have additional features that could reveal effector
595 activity. Again, the emblematic example is the HC-Pro of potyviruses that can hinder the plant
596 RNAi machinery, but other HCs, less understood, can also block the microtubular network (P2
597 of CaMV) (Blanc et al., 1996), induce membrane fusion (NSvc2C of RSV) (Lu et al., 2019) or
598 interact with stress granules (NSP of PNYDV) (Krapp et al., 2017). That they interact with
599 highly symmetrically arranged coat proteins, either icosahedral or helicoïdal, offers multiple
600 attachment sites per particle and ensures that a high number of HCs can potentially be
601 retained in and be released from the vector together with virions. The amount of HC molecules
602 delivered could even be larger when HCs are prone to self-oligomerization as is the case for
603 HC-Pro of potyviruses, P2 of CaMV, NSP of nanoviruses and NSvc2 of RSV. Hence,
604 mobilizing a limited number of receptors in the vector may allow hundreds of HC molecules to
605 be retained and/or internalized and later inoculated into the plant. The present paradigm
606 regarding the primary role of an HC could completely change by considering that it could be
607 an effector useful to the virus upon arrival in a cell and that its binding to the virus particles
608 and to the vector would merely ensure that it travels and is delivered with it. Whether HCs are
609 released together with virions within host plant cells is not known but investigation of this
610 question would be relevant for this hypothesis. It is also important to note that the “effector”
611 hypothesis could apply to all reported HCs described, and that the effector function may either
612 act in host plant cells, in vector cells, or both.

613 **6 Conclusion**

614 In conclusion, several potential benefits associated to the helper strategy are imaginable. We
615 insisted in this conclusion that each of this benefit could apply to all cases described, whatever
616 the viral clade concerned. However, we cannot exclude that distinct helpers have evolved for
617 distinct reasons and perhaps, other potential explanation are still to be conceived.
618 Unfortunately, as they stand, the here-described hypothesis, with perhaps the exception of
619 the “effector hypothesis” are not empirically testable, maintaining the question of the raison

620 d'être of HCs a major conceptual challenge for future research in plant virology and vector
621 transmission.

Table 1: List of viral families and genera where HCs have been identified

Virus family ^a	Virus genus ^a	Virus name/acronym ^a	HC name/acronym	Transmission mode	Vector taxon	First HC-describing reference
<i>Potyviridae</i>	<i>Potyvirus</i>	Potato virus Y (PVY)	Helper-component proteinase (HC-Pro)	Non-circulative	Aphids	Kassanis and Govier 1971a,b
	<i>Tritimovirus</i>	Sweet potato mild mottle virus (SPMMV)			Whiteflies	Colinet et al 1998
	<i>Ipomovirus</i>	Wheat streak mosaic virus (WSMV)			Mites	Stenger et al 2005
<i>Caulimoviridae</i>	<i>Caulimovirus</i>	Cauliflower mosaic virus (CaMV)	Aphid transmission factor (P2)		Aphids	Lung and Pirone 1973
<i>Virgaviridae</i>	<i>Tobravirus</i>	Tobacco rattle virus (TBRV)	Protein 2b		Nematodes	McFarlane et al 1996
<i>Phenuiviridae</i>	<i>Tenuivirus</i>	Rice stripe virus (RSV)	Non-structural glycoprotein 2 (NSvc2)	Circulative propagative	Plant hoppers	Lu et al 2019
<i>Nanoviridae</i>	<i>Babuvirus</i>	Faba bean necrotic yellows virus (FBNSV)	Nuclear shuttle protein (NSP)	Circulative non-propagative	Aphids	Franz et al 1999
	<i>Nanovirus</i> ^b					

^a Families and genera listed in this table are only those where the HC has been identified. The existence of an HC has been suggested in others but not identified.

^b Babuviruses have a DNA segment highly homologous to the segment N (encoding NSP) of nanoviruses and so its role as a HC makes little doubt though the lack of infectious clones has precluded definitive proof.

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Conflict of Interest Disclosure

The authors of this preprint declare that they have no financial conflict of interest with the content of this article.

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